

Identifying Computational Thinking Behaviors in the Robotics Programming Activity*

Megumi Iwata¹[0000-0001-7944-5157], Kateryna Zabolotna¹[0000-0003-3920-9859],
Kati Mäkitalo¹[0000-0003-4037-2872], Jari Laru¹[0000-0003-0347-0182], and
Jonna Malmberg¹[0000-0002-8890-4068]

University of Oulu, Pentti Kaiteran katu 1, 90570 Oulu, Finland
`megumi.iwata@oulu.fi`

Abstract. Robotics programming is a context which can enhance the development of computational thinking (CT) by demonstrating abstract concepts in a concrete way. Assessing applied CT components from behavioral observation has not yet been studied extensively. We aim to advance the means to identify CT behaviors in a robotics programming activity. In this paper, we introduce a pilot study where we examine an existing CT behavior scheme by applying it into the robotics programming contexts. The ninth grade students worked on the tasks of building the robot arm and programming it to make different movements. We analysed the video data to identify CT behaviors in their interactions. All items in the CT behavior scheme were observed in the robotics programming activity. CT behaviors were observed most in the independent programming phase. The students applied CT while testing the commands and debugging. In the building phase the complex process with the physical materials increased the opportunity to apply decomposition and abstraction. The results indicate that the structured instructional design of the activity minimised the students' freedom, creativity and thinking, which might limit the chance to apply CT components. We conclude that CT behavior scheme can be used in the robotics programming contexts, however, modifications in the descriptions of the items to adjust to the robotics contexts are necessary. The findings contribute to the CT research community by advancing the methodological approach of assessing CT and by deepening the understanding of the robotics programming as the contexts to use the CT components.

Keywords: Computational thinking · Behavioral observation · Robotics programming

1 Introduction

Computational thinking (CT) is considered as the cognitive aspect of computational literacies [10] and the necessary skill for everyone [21]. In Finland, CT is

* This study was supported by the GenZ strategic profiling project of the University of Oulu funded by the Academy of Finland [project No.318930] and the University of Oulu. The data collection was carried out with the support of Leaf Research Infrastructure, University of Oulu, Finland.

a part of the national framework of digital competence which applies to early childhood education and care, pre-primary education and nine-year of primary and lower secondary education (comprehensive school) [6]. CT has been studied most extensively in the past 10 years [15]. Yet, definition of CT is still under discussion. One of the frequently used definitions was provided by Aho summarising CT as “the thought processes involved in formulating problems so their solutions can be represented as computational steps and algorithms” (p. 832) [1]. Recognising CT as a transferable competence beyond programming and computing, Ezeamuzie and colleagues defining CT as “the cognitive skill required to design algorithmic solutions for problems in different knowledge areas” (p.502) [5].

In more practical level, researchers have proposed operational definitions of CT mapping the concepts, the processes, and the practices underlying when CT is applied. In this paper, we call them as CT components. We select the four CT components: problem decomposition, abstraction, pattern recognition and algorithm design, which are identified as the common CT components [3,20]. Decomposition is understood as simplifying a problem/task by dissecting it into manageable parts that can be addressed separately [3,17]. Abstraction is a practice of concentrating on the essential part to solve a problem/task while concealing minor details [3,5]. Pattern recognition is identifying patterns/rules based on observations and applying these rules to a other instance [3,17]. Algorithm design is formulating logical and ordered instructions to solve a problem/task translating abstract ideas into concrete procedure [3,17].

Robotics programming can be an effective way to introduce CT in K-12 education [12,16]. A constructivist learning environment can support understanding and demonstrating the abstract concept of CT in a concrete way [8]. In addition, the use of physical materials increases cognitive challenges by adding another layer of complexity in the activity, which can enhance the use of CT [13,9]. The previous study indicates that the middle school students prefer to learn computing with hands-on physical computing environments compared to screen-based computing environments [12]. The authors indicate that open-ended activity design appears to increase students’ interests and confidence in coding despite of the additional challenges of troubleshooting with physical components.

There has been an increasing interest in studying the assessment of CT in the past years. The most common assessment methods of assessing CT competences are pre- and post-test, self-report and artifact analysis [19]. Using observation as a assessment method allows assessing CT competences directly in the activity which provide richer and content-related information of students’ CT competences [14]. The structured systematic observation was used to assess the students’ competences in the block-based programming contexts using Scratch [14]. One of the scales of the structured systematic observation was “computational concepts” which lists six items to assess the students’ competence. Observational analysis was used to identify the development of CT of 5-year-old children [18]. The authors assessed CT through analysing the movement of the robot that the children controlled. However, assessing CT through behavioral observation has not been well studied [3].

In this study, we aim to advance the behavioral observation method to identify applied CT components from the students' interactions in the robotics programming activities. We conduct a pilot study where we apply an existing framework of CT behavior scheme to examine its usability in the robotics programming contexts. We set the following two research questions.

- 1 Which CT components are present in the robotics programming activity?
- 2 To what extent are the CT behaviors observed in students' interactions in the different phases of the robotics programming activity?

This study contributes CT research community by deepening the conceptual understanding of CT in robotics programming contexts and by developing behavioral observation as a methodological approach to identifying the use of the CT components.

2 Related Work

2.1 CT in the Robotics Programming Contexts

In robotics activities, students are encouraged to actively interact with the physical objects, to play and to design. Often the robotics activities were designed as student-centered and facilitated by the instructors who help students in the programming and other challenges [8]. A previous study shows that minimum instructions encourages students' trials-and-errors behavior [4].

There are a view of CT in robotics that claims that CT appears when the students program to make the robot move [8,4]. On the other hand, there is broader view that CT is not limited to the programming part of the robotics activities, but it appears in all phases of robotics activities. The latest study propose six components of CT in robotics activities recognising CT as an approach applying computer science concepts and procedures to understand, model, and solve a problem using tangible objects or programming software [13]. The proposed components are divided into three categories: problem analysis, systems and creation, which includes two components in each category: identify the problem, organise and model the problem, formal system (software), physical system (tangible objects), devise a solution, and evaluate the solution and perform iteration [13].

2.2 Frameworks for Identifying CT Behaviors

To our knowledge, two frameworks for observing CT behaviors have been introduced. Computational Thinking Behavior Scheme (CTBS) was developed by Boom and colleagues to identify CT behaviors in block-based programming contexts using Scratch [3]. The framework defines four CT components (decomposition, abstraction, pattern recognition and algorithm design). CTBS lists 11 items as behavior indicators to identify the applied CT components. The observation of CT behaviors are done by measuring the time spent rather than correctness

of the applied CT [3]. The authors found the correlation between the applied CT components and the quality of the end results (the programming projects in Scratch). They note that the instrument was developed specifically to the context of their study, thus the items should be examined carefully.

Another framework focuses on the CT components in the robotics contexts. Keith and colleagues developed the coding system for CT in the robotics activity for the children aged 8-13 using LEGO Mindstorms EV3 robotics kit [11]. The framework categorises four CT components (analysis, algorithmic thinking, debugging and designing). The framework was developed considering the characteristics of the robotics contexts. For example, design of the robot is considered as one aspect to support the use of CT components [11].

After examining the two frameworks above, we decided to use CTBS in the following pilot study. The reason is because, firstly, it was valid in some extent as the authors found that the CT components observed with CTBS are correlated with the quality of the program. Secondly, lack of items related to the programming in the framework by Keith and colleagues can be challenging to adapt to our pilot study, which has both building and programming phases.

3 Research Methods

3.1 The Context of the Study: Robotics Programming Workshop

Participants of the Workshop This pilot study was implemented in the two-day robotics programming workshop organised and facilitated by the researchers. The workshop was offered as a part of a week-long work-life orientation¹, which is required in the Finnish National Core Curriculum for Basic Education. Participants of the workshop included 21 ninth grade students in the international school in Finland. Among several other options, the students chose to participate in this workshop by themselves. There was no requirement of the prior knowledge to participate for the workshop. Nevertheless the students had been introduced to programming within the Finnish National Core Curriculum for Basic Education.

Description of the Tasks The goal of the workshop was building the robot arm and programming it to make different movements. The robot arm called "Alvin" and the software application to program Alvin were designed and provided by a company in Finland². In the workshop, the students worked as a group of two or three following the provided instructions. No strict timetable was provided, thus each group worked on the tasks on their own pace. The instructors were available if the students needed additional help. The tasks of the workshop were divided into two phases: building phase and programming phase, as described below.

¹ Työelämään tutustuminen (TET) in Finnish

² <https://simua.com/>

Building Phase In the building phase the students assembled the robot arm (Fig. 1). The robot arm was made from the pre-cut wooden parts, six servo motors and a microcontroller (ESP32). The students assembled them using the screws, the hammer and other tools. The base part of the robot arm can be rotated and the arm part can be flexed and extended with the joints. It has the hand part that can rotate, open and close to grab objects. The video instructions were provided to support the students in the building phase. The purpose of this phase was to build the same functional robot that can be programmed rather than designing and creating their own artifacts using their creativity. Although these instructions explained the steps in detail, the students had a chance to make decisions of how they approach to the tasks.

Fig. 1: Robot arm Alvin

Programming Phase After building the robot arm, the students started programming to make different movements. The goal of the programming phase was creating procedures (collection of movements) by combining the different pre-programmed movements. The pre-programmed movements included turn, bow and bend, and open and close the hand, which can be used with the structures, such as for-loop, while-loop. Programming was done by sending the commands through the software application on the tablet device. The interface of the software application was designed as if communicating with the robot with text messages (Fig. 3). For instance, to bend the robot arm, the movements of each servo motor can be programmed by sending the commands, such as "move the servo 1 for 40 degrees". The printed booklet instructions³ including guidance for programming and the exercises were provided (Fig. 2).

Guided Programming Phase During the programming phase, the instructor held the short lecture, where they went through the beginning of the programming part in the booklet instructions together with the students. They explained how

³ The booklet was still a prototype and not a commercial product.

Fig. 2: Booklet instructions

Fig. 3: Programming interface

to send the commands, how to create classes, how to test the commands in the interface, and how to create and execute procedures. In the data analysis, we called this lecture as guided programming phase, and other moments, when the students worked on the programming exercises by themselves, as independent programming phase.

3.2 Data of the Study and Analysis

Data Collection and Ethical Consideration The data collection was carried out with the support of Leaf Research Infrastructure⁴, at the University of Oulu, Finland. The data of this pilot study was the video of a group of two students recorded on the second day. The video included both building and programming phases. The length of the video was 8394 seconds (140 minutes). The video was taken in front of the desk where the students were sitting. On the desk, the robot arm was clearly visible. The video did not show the programming interface, so the log data was used to understand the processes of the programming phase.

The data collection was carried out as a part of a larger research program, the GenZ profiling project of the University of Oulu. It was approved by the ethical committee of the university and was carried out according to the national and international ethical guidelines [2,7]. Informed consent was collected from both participants and their guardians. Students' names were replaced with ID numbers (pseudonymized) prior to data processing.

Data Analysis The data analysis was conducted in *the Observer XT* environment. The unit of the data analysis was group rather than individuals. We first identified the process of the activity by categorising into three phases: building phase, individual programming phase and guided programming phase. We then divided the students' interactions into "on-task interaction" and "off-task interaction" to remove irrelevant moments. The interactions between the students

⁴ <https://www.oulu.fi/en/research/research-infrastructures/leaf-research-infrastructure>

and the instructors, which subject was related to the task, were coded as an on-task interaction. After that, we conducted coding of the CT behaviors based on CTBS. Appendix 1 shows CT behavior scheme by Boom and colleagues [3] with the adjustments in the behavior indicators to make it suitable to the contexts. We changed the term "code blocks" and "code chunks" to "commands" and "story or game" to "pieces". In the analysis we focused on "meaningful episode" in the activity, where the students applied the CT components. A meaningful episode included the students' interactions with silence of less than 10 seconds. We calculated the duration and the frequency of each item in Observer XT in order to analyse how the CT components appeared during the activity.

We did not include as CT behavior when the students were working on the task but the interactions did not include their active thinking on the task. For instance, when the students were identifying the next step by just checking the instruction without discussing it, we did not code as CT behavior.

Student A: *OK, what's next?*

Student B: (Watching the video) *Ah... this part.*

Neither we coded as CT behavior if a student just tell the other what to do.

Student A: *Take that off.*

Student B: *OK.*

Another example of non-CT behavior was when the students had an unclear issue but did not engage in discussing.

Student A: *Is there a limit to the bend?*

Student B: *I don't know. (Change the subject.)*

4 Results

Table 2 shows the length of each phase. The building phase lasted for 3249 seconds (54 minutes, 38.7% of the total length of the video). It started in the beginning of the activity as the students were continuing building the robot arm from the previous day. The independent programming phase took place after the building phase for 3751 seconds (63 minutes, 44.7% of the total length of the video). The guided programming phase, which was in the middle of the independent programming phase, was 1168 seconds (19 minutes, 13.9% of the total length of the video). The length of the on-task interactions was 5696 seconds (95 minutes, 67.9% of the total length of the video).

Table 1: Phases of the robotics programming activity

	Building	Independent programming	Guided programming	Other	Total
Duration (s)	3249	3751	1168	226	8394
Percentage (%)	38.7	44.7	13.9	2.7	100.0

4.1 CT Behaviors Observed in the Robotics Programming Activity

The CT behaviors observed in the three phases of the robotics programming activity are summarised in Table 3 in Appendix 2. All four CT components in CTBS were observed in the video data. Total duration of the meaningful episodes was 2596 seconds (43 minutes) and it was 31% of the total length of the video. Total frequency of the moments, which CT behaviors were observed, was 158 times. Among the CT components, "algorithm design" (ALG) was observed most frequently (133 times) and the longest duration (2082 seconds). The second most frequent CT component was "decomposition", which total duration was 299 seconds and observed 36 times. Between the two least observed CT components, "abstraction" was observed longer duration (136 seconds) than pattern recognition (80 seconds).

Independent Programming Phase The CT behaviors were observed the most in the independent programming phase. In total the CT behaviors were observed 119 times and the duration was 1812 seconds which is around 70% of the total CT behaviors. In the independent programming phase, most of the CT behaviors were directly related to the process of designing algorithms in the commands. Below is an example of CT behaviors from the independent programming phase with the CTBS items assigned (see Appendix 1).

Example The students were teaching the robot a new movement "dance move" which combined several movements that they have previously tested. Student A read the instructions and suggested the steps to proceed while Student B held the tablet to program the robot arm.

Student A: *Let's start (writing) "To make dance move" (command) and then "Make dance move" (command)* [DCM1, DCM2].

Then two students discussed the content of the commands, for example, degrees of turning and the order of the movements in "the dance move" [ALG1]. After that, the students sent the commands and observed the robot arm checking whether the robot arm moved as expected [ALG2]. As there was an error, the students tried to fix the error [ALG3].

Building Phase About 20% of the CT behaviors were observed in the building phase. In the building phase, the students had many problems with the physical materials, where the CT behavior of debugging was observed. In addition, the process of the building was complex as they needed assemble many parts in the correct orders. In such process, the CT behaviors of decomposition and abstraction was used. Below is an example of debugging in the building phase, which was coded under the CTBS item [ALG3].

Example The students were trying to assemble a part on the robot arm with several screws. Student A held the screw driver and Student B held the part and the robot arm together. While screwing the students realized that the part was

not aligned anymore. The students decided to unscrew and try again.

Student B: *Wait wait wait. You are not...*

Student A: *Ohh it is not?*

Student B: *You're punching through the thingy (wooden piece) for some reason.*

Student A: *Right. Maybe it's not aligned with the hole.*

Student B: *There is no hole, right?*

Student A: *There's a hole used to be.*

Student B: *There is?*

Student A: *Yeah there is. Wait. Right, let's totally unscrew this and then...*

Guided Programming Phase In the guided programming phase, the CT behaviors were least observed. Less than 10% of the CT behaviors were present in the guided programming phase. As an example of CT behaviors from the guided programming phase is as follows.

Example The students were learning the basics of programming following the instructor's example command. The students discussed the content of the example command [ALG1]. Then they checked that it worked [ALG2].

After that the students wanted to customise the example command but they did not find how to do it. The students asked the instructor. The below interaction was coded as pattern recognition and algorithms [PTR2, ALG1].

Student A: *What if we later on want to add something into the procedure? How to do that?*

Instructor: *You can ask Alvin how to do that. And you can copy paste, and modify and edit any text, and overwrite. . .*

Student A: *Ah.*

Student B: *Select all, copy, then paste.*

5 Discussion and Conclusion

5.1 Usability of CTBS in the Robotics Contexts

In this study we tested the existing framework of identifying the behaviors for applied CT components in the new context. All the items in CTBS were observed in the video data of the pilot study. Thus, even though CTBS was originally developed for the block-based programming context, it is possible to apply it into the robotics programming contexts. The CT behaviors were observed most in the independent programming phase. This is understandable as it is closest to the context which CTBS was originally developed. In the guiding programming phase, the least CT behaviors were present. This was also expected as the students were mostly listening the instructor's short lecture and there were less interactions between the students.

The building phase, which is unique to the robotics contexts, although the CT behaviors were observed, the overall presence was far less than the independent programming phase. One reason is because the coding framework was not

optimised for the robotics contexts. Some of the behavioral indicators in CTBS, such as PTR2 ("Use of copy-paste"), were more closely related to programming (see Appendix 1). The behavioral indicators can be modified further to adapt the characteristics of the robotics contexts. For instance, in the building phase, the students observed the model of the robot arm while assembling their own. This could be considered as copy-paste in robotics contexts as they were transferring the observed constructions to their own context. Another item: ALG1 ("Putting commands together"), could be modified to the robotics programming contexts by adding descriptions related to physical materials, such as "Identifying the steps and the order to assemble the parts".

5.2 Influences of the Activity Design on the Use of CT

Complexity in Building Phase "Decomposition" and "abstraction" were somewhat observed in the independent programming and the building phases. It was more present in the building phase than programming phases. One reason might be that there were more complexity in the building phase, including many steps involving different physical parts needed to be assembled in the correct orientation and the correct order. The use of CT in the complex process including physical materials are discussed also in the previous studies [13,9]. In the complex process, the students had to discuss and agreed on the steps to proceed. Compared to the building phase, the programming phase was more simplified and straightforward. The level of programming was rather low, the interface was easy to use and the detailed instructions were provided.

Structured Activity with Step-by-Step Instructions Both "Decomposition" and "abstraction" are considered as part of problem analysis [13]. Because the instructions were provided, which included each step to build the robot arm and many example commands, in most of the tasks the students did not need to analyse the problems and plan the procedure by themselves. The complex problems were already divided into small pieces and written as step-by-step instructions. The students were strictly following the instructions, thus their focus was fixed to the immediate next steps rather than the further goals. This may be the reason of why DCM2 ("Identifying the immediate next step") was most observed among "decomposition" items. If the students have more freedom in the tasks, they may have more chances to plan their tasks.

Limited Possibility of Customisation "Pattern recognition", which was the least observed CT components in our study, is the skill to identifying the similar characteristics (rules) to transfer them into the different contexts [3]. This can appear, for example, in the process of customising the commands. However, in the pilot study, the students did not have enough opportunity to customise the commands by themselves as the instructions in the activity were quite complete and not encouraging making modifications. Design and creativity are the aspects that is important in the robotics contexts [11,13]. Building of the robot arm could

be designed as ill-structured allowing the students to personalise the robot, which can increase their interests [12] and the chance to apply the CT components.

5.3 Limitation of the Study and Future Research Direction

A limitation of this study is the small amount of data. Only part of one group's activity was analysed. This was partially because the aim of the pilot study was to test the preliminary usability of CTBS in the robotics contexts for the further development. The next step of the research is to test the updated CTBS with other participants in the same workshop. Another limitation is related to the data analysis. In the data analysis, the on-task interactions with maximum of 10 seconds silence was conducted before coding of the CT behaviors. Thus, some moments of applied CT components, which were not discussed between the students, might be excluded from the CT behaviors. For example, in the guiding programming phase, the students were mostly silence, although they were following the instructions and programming the robot arm. This needs to be examined carefully in the future research. Finally, due to the time constraint, validation of the coding was incomplete. As the coding process of identifying CT behavior is subjective, we recognise that the validation of the coding scheme is the immediate next task.

To conclude, this study found the possibility of assessing applied CT components through behavioral observation in the robotics programming activity using CTBS. The framework should be adjusted to the contexts and further examination is needed. The robotics programming contexts added complexity in the activity by involving physical materials. The instructional design should be considered carefully to increase the chance to apply CT in the activity. In a structured activity, students' freedom and creativity are minimised and it can result in limiting their own thinking and the opportunity to use CT. The activity should be designed to maintain the balance of task difficulties and the space for student's freedom, creativity and thinking.

6 Appendix 1

CT components	Behavioral indicator	Example episode
Decomposition (DCM)	DCM1: Putting problem into pieces / building sub problems DCM2: Identifying the immediate next step DCM3: Discussing if then relations of the pieces (is related to programming elements)	Students discuss the current step as a part of the overall process: <i>Should all the pieces have to be assembled?</i>
Abstraction (ABS)	ABS1: Focusing on important information; neglecting unimportant details ABS2: Simplifying anything problem, sub problem, functions, commands, etc.	Students neglect a part of the process: <i>We don't need to do everything yet.</i>
Pattern recognition (PTR)	PTR1: Identifying similar characteristics (sub problem, functions, commands etc.) PTR2: Use of copy-paste PTR3: Aha moments (must be related to an event when student understood relationship between things)	Students recognise the similarities in the process: <i>It's all of these, right? So just go like this. I think it's just way easier.</i>
Algorithm design (ALG)	ALG1: Putting commands together ALG2: Testing and judging algorithm (i.e., run a set of code and actively observing a running sequence) ALG3: Debugging - try to find error and adjust algorithm	Students discuss which parts should be assembled in which order: <i>This part needs to be put through here, and after that put this one.</i>

CT components and the behavior indicators were adapted from CT behavior scheme by Boom and colleagues [3]. The terms in the behavior indicators were modified and the example episodes were added by the authors.

7 Appendix 2

CTBS item ¹	Building		Independent programming		Guided programming		Phases total	
	Duration ²	Freq. ³	Duration	Freq.	Duration	Freq.	Duration	Freq.
DCM1	- (-)	- (-)	8 (100.0)	1 (100.0)	- (-)	- (-)	8 (100.0)	1 (100.0)
DCM2	157 (55.8)	14 (42.4)	125 (44.2)	19 (57.6)	- (0.0)	- (0.0)	282 (100.0)	33 (100.0)
DCM3	9 (100.0)	2 (100.0)	- (0.0)	- (0.0)	- (0.0)	- (0.0)	9 (100.0)	2 (100.0)
DCM total	166 (55.7)	16 (44.4)	125 (44.3)	19 (55.6)	- (0.0)	- (0.0)	299 (100.0)	36 (100.0)
ABS1	101 (100.0)	2 (100.0)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	101 (100.0)	2 (100.0)
ABS2	24 (68.8)	1 (50.0)	11 (31.2)	1 (0.0)	- (0.0)	- (0.0)	34 (100.0)	2 (100.0)
ABS total	125 (92.1)	3 (75.0)	10.7 (31.2)	1 (25.0)	- (0.0)	- (0.0)	136 (100.0)	4 (100.0)
PTR1	19 (100.0)	2 (100.0)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	19 (100.0)	2 (100.0)
PTR2	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	- (-)	17 (100.0)	1 (100.0)	17 (100.0)	1 (100.0)
PTR3	- (-)	- (-)	31 (70.0)	1(50.0)	13 (30.0)	1(50.0)	44 (100.0)	2(100.0)
PTR total	19 (23.8)	2 (40.0)	31 (38.5)	1 (20.0)	30 (37.7)	2 (40.0)	80 (100.0)	5 (100.0)
ALG1	4 (0.9)	1 (2.8)	318 (68.0)	30 (83.3)	145 (31.1)	5 (13.9)	447 (100.0)	36 (100.0)
ALG2	20 (2.6)	1 (2.1)	716 (96.5)	45 (93.8)	7 (0.9)	2 (4.2)	742 (100.0)	48 (100.0)
ALG3	287 (30.8)	7 (24.1)	605 (69.2)	22 (75.9)	- (0.0)	- (0.0)	874 (100.0)	29 (100.0)
ALG total	293 (14.1)	9 (8.0)	1638 (78.7)	97 (85.8)	152 (7.3)	7 (6.2)	2082 (100.0)	133 (100.0)
CT total	603 (23.2)	30 (19.0)	1812 (69.8)	119 (75.3)	181 (7.0)	9 (5.7)	2596 (100.0)	158 (100.0)

¹ See Appendix 1 for the descriptions of CTBS items.

² Duration of the item in the phase. Unit is second. () after the value indicates the percentage of the total duration of the item in all phases.

³ Frequency of the item in the phase. Unit is n. () after the value indicates the percentage of the total frequency of the item in all phases.

References

1. Aho, A.V.: Computation and computational thinking. *The computer journal* **55**(7), 832–835 (2012)
2. ALLEA - All European Academies: The european code of conduct for research integrity revised edition (2017), <https://www.allea.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/ALLEA-European-Code-of-Conduct-for-Research-Integrity-2017.pdf>, last accessed 14 August 2023
3. Boom, K.D., Bower, M., Siemon, J., Arguel, A.: Relationships between computational thinking and the quality of computer programs. *Education and Information Technologies* **27**(6), 8289–8310 (2022)
4. Chevalier, M., Giang, C., Piatti, A., Mondada, F.: Fostering computational thinking through educational robotics: A model for creative computational problem solving. *International Journal of STEM Education* **7**(1), 1–18 (2020)
5. Ezeamuzie, N.O., Leung, J.S.: Computational thinking through an empirical lens: A systematic review of literature. *Journal of Educational Computing Research* **60**(2), 481–511 (2022)
6. Finnish National Agency for Education: The framework for digital competence (2023), <https://eperusteet.opintopolku.fi/#/en/digiosaaminen/8706410/osaamiskokonaisuus/8709075>, last accessed 4 August 2023
7. Finnish National Board on Research Integrity TENK: The ethical principles of research with human participants and ethical review in the human sciences in finland (2019), https://tenk.fi/sites/default/files/2021-01/Ethical_review_in_human_sciences_2020.pdf, last accessed 14 August 2023
8. Ioannou, A., Makridou, E.: Exploring the potentials of educational robotics in the development of computational thinking: A summary of current research and practical proposal for future work. *Education and Information Technologies* **23**, 2531–2544 (2018)
9. Iwata, M., Pitkänen, K., Laru, J., Mäkitalo, K.: Exploring potentials and challenges to develop twenty-first century skills and computational thinking in k-12 maker education. In: *Frontiers in Education*. vol. 5, p. 87. Frontiers Media SA (2020)
10. Kafai, Y.B., Proctor, C.: A revaluation of computational thinking in k–12 education: Moving toward computational literacies. *Educational Researcher* **51**(2), 146–151 (2022)
11. Keith, P.K., Sullivan, F.R., Pham, D.: Roles, collaboration, and the development of computational thinking in a robotics learning environment. *Computational thinking education* pp. 223–245 (2019)
12. Love, T.S., Asempapa, R.S.: A screen-based or physical computing unit? examining secondary students’ attitudes toward coding. *International Journal of Child-Computer Interaction* **34**, 100543 (2022)
13. Romero, M.: Assessment of computational thinking in an ill-defined problem-solving task with modular robots. In: *International Conference of the Learning Sciences (ICLS)*. Montreal, Canada (2023)
14. Saez-Lopez, J.M., Marcos, R.G., Esteban, V.C.: Visual programming languages integrated across the curriculum in elementary school: A two year case study using “scratch” in five schools. *Computers & Education* (2016)
15. Saqr, M., Ng, K., Oyelere, S.S., Tedre, M.: People, ideas, milestones: a scientometric study of computational thinking. *ACM Transactions on Computing Education (TOCE)* **21**(3), 1–17 (2021)

16. Shahin, M., Gonsalvez, C., Whittle, J., Chen, C., Li, L., Xia, X.: How secondary school girls perceive computational thinking practices through collaborative programming with the micro: bit. *Journal of Systems and Software* **183**, 111107 (2022)
17. Shute, V.J., Sun, C., Asbell-Clarke, J.: Demystifying computational thinking. *Educational research review* **22**, 142–158 (2017)
18. Terroba, M., Ribera, J.M., Lapresa, D., Anguera, M.T.: Observational analysis of the development of computational thinking in early childhood education (5 years old) through an intervention proposal with a ground robot of programmed directionality. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal* **30**(3), 437–455 (2022)
19. Tikva, C., Tambouris, E.: Mapping computational thinking through programming in k-12 education: A conceptual model based on a systematic literature review. *Computers & Education* **162**, 104083 (2021)
20. Wang, C., Shen, J., Chao, J.: Integrating computational thinking in stem education: A literature review. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education* **20**(8), 1949–1972 (2022)
21. Wing, J.M.: Computational thinking and thinking about computing. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences* **366**(1881), 3717–3725 (2008)